

Physico-Chemical Evidence for the Analogy between the Complexes of Iron(II) and(III) with Octacoordinated Cyanotungstate(IV) and Cyanomolybdate(IV) and the Iron Blues

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Iron(II) and (III) react with $K_4Mo(CN)_8$, $K_4W(CN)_8$ and $K_3Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)$ to give blue 1:1 complexes. The iron(II) complexes are initially yellow but turn blue on standing, even in vacuum. Magnetic measurements show the complex to be diamagnetic while the iron complexes formed are paramagnetic with unpaired spins greater than 4.5 and upto 5.0, showing that iron may be in the +3 state even in the case of complexes formed from Fe(II). Mössbauer spectra support this view point that iron in the +3 oxidation state and the color change from yellow to blue may be due to oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III). These complexes are therefore similar to the Iron Blues (Prussian and Turnbull's blue) where in the final product we have Fe(III) outside the coordination sphere irrespective of the fact that the complex was prepared from either Fe(II) or Fe(III). These complexes may thus be termed as 'Iron Blue Analogs'.

BARBEIRI¹ for the first time reported the color reaction of iron(II) and (III) with octacyanomolybdate(IV) and (V), which is accompanied by yellow to blue color change. This reaction has been studied by Malik and Ali² who found that the complex formed has 1:1 stoichiometry. This 1:1 stoichiometry and the color change from yellow to blue is similar to the iron blues prepared from iron and ferrocyanides/ferricyanides. A similar color change is observed on interacting Fe(II) and (III) with $K_4Mo(CN)_8$, $K_4W(CN)_8$ and $K_3Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)$. Studies have been thus carried out to establish the analogy between these complexes and the 'Iron Blues'.

Experimental

Potassium octacyanomolybdate(IV), Potassium tetracyano trihydroxo (aquo) molybdate (IV) and potassium octacyanotungstate (IV) were prepared by the method of Furman and Miller³, Jacob⁴ and Kosinska and Stasicka⁵ respectively.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate and ferric ammonium sulphate were AnalaR grade, BDH products.

Conductance measurements were made on Toshniwal (India) conductivity bridge type CLOI/01A at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. A Toshniwal polarograph type CLO2 A in conjunction with a pye sealampgalvanometer was used for amperometric titrations using a d.m.c. (capillary characteristic $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.95$).

Magnetic measurements were carried out by Gouy's method at room temperature ($25^\circ \pm 1.0^\circ$). The infra-

red spectra were recorded on Beckmann IR20 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets in the 4000-250 cm^{-1} range. Mössbauer spectra were obtained with Mössbauer spectrometer MBS35 supplied by ECIL, Hyderabad. It consisted of a single channel analyser and electronic linear velocity loud speaker drive using a $3mCi/Co^{57}$ source in Rh matrix. The spectrometer was calibrated against standard sodium nitroprusside and iron foil. Due to large scattering by molybdenum and tungsten, the counting at each channel was carried out for 500 sec. and the spectra recorded in triplicate.

Isolation of the complexes: Ferrous ammonium sulphate or ferric ammonium sulphate were mixed with the cyano complex in the ratio of 1:1 using concentrations of about 0.1M. On mixing an immediate color change took place and a colloidal solution was obtained. This solution was centrifuged for 5 min at 1000 r.p.m., then treated with twice its volume of acetone and allowed to stand for half an hour. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with acetone-water mixture (1:1), then acetone and finally with ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The solution of iron(II) and(III) should be acidic to avoid precipitation of the iron hydroxides. In the case of iron(II) a yellow colored precipitate is obtained which changes to blue in a few hours. The color change takes place even in vacuum.

Chemical analysis: Metal estimation was performed by decomposing the complex with boiling

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aqua regia and estimating iron as Fe_2O_3 and molybdenum and tungsten as oxinates⁶. Water was estimated by desiccating the complex at 110° . Nitrogen was estimated at the Chemical Laboratories, Punjab University, Chandigarh.

Results and Discussion

Malik and Ali² showed that the blue complex obtained from Fe(III) and $[\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ has λ_{max} at 840 nm and their combining ratio is 1:1. This has been verified by conductometric and amperometric titrations, which also show that the complexes of Fe(II) and Fe(III) with the other octacoordinated cyanomolybdates and tungstates are also 1:1 complexes.

The room temperature molar susceptibilities (uncorrected for underlying diamagnetism) were found to be -215.49×10^{-6} , -220.07×10^{-6} and -116.88×10^{-6} cgs unit/mole for $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively showing them to be diamagnetic. The compound potassium tetracyano trihydroxo (aquo) molybdate (IV) has been formulated as $\text{K}_3\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ by Bucknall and Wardlaw⁷ but Griffith *et al*⁸ have formulated it as $\text{K}_3\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_4$, showing paramagnetism. The blue aquo complex prepared in this laboratory was definitely diamagnetic and none of the samples prepared during the course of these

investigations were found to provide any evidence for paramagnetic behaviour. The complex may, therefore, be formulated according to Bucknall and Wardlaw⁷. The diamagnetic character of this complex implies that a spin paired complex with d^4sp^3 hybridisation is formed and hence a dodecahedral structure may be expected.

Magnetic measurements (Table 1) show that all the six iron complexes are paramagnetic and their magnetic moments are falling in two categories: (a) with magnetic moment in the range 5.6-5.7 (4.5-4.6 unpaired spins) for the iron(II) complexes, (b) with magnetic moments in the range 6.1-6.2 (5 unpaired spins) for the iron(III) complexes. Since the parent compounds are all diamagnetic, it is evident that the paramagnetic character is due to the Fe(II) and Fe(III) atoms and also that iron is forming spin free complex⁹. It may thus be concluded that just like the heteropolyferrocyanides¹⁰⁻¹¹, these complexes are also spin free and their magnetic moment is approximately equal to that of diamagnetic Mo^{IV} and W^{IV} plus Fe(II) and Fe(III). However, in the case of Fe(II) complexes, the magnetic moments show 4.5 unpaired spins, whence it cannot be definitely said whether iron is in the +2 or +3 state. This is also supported by the fact that initially the Fe(II) complexes are yellow and then turn blue, probably due to oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III).

TABLE 1. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Chemical analysis								magnetic moment BM	number of unpaired spins
	% Found				% Calcd					
	Mo/W	Fe	N	H ₂ O	Mo/W	Fe	N	H ₂ O		
Complex of Fe(II) with $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6$	19.97	12.03	23.30	7.81	20.24	11.78	23.63	7.74	5.66	4.57
$\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_6$	32.31	9.93	20.18	6.58	32.69	9.76	19.92	6.47	5.68	4.59
$\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	24.34	13.78	13.78	9.16	23.98	13.96	13.86	9.00	5.61	4.61
Complex of Fe(III) with $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6$	22.41	12.84	25.76	8.41	22.05	13.06	25.52	8.28	6.10	5.02
$\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_6$	35.54	10.68	21.43	6.76	35.16	10.81	21.19	6.93	6.00	4.92
$\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	26.58	15.47	15.22	8.71	26.26	15.64	15.39	8.98	6.15	5.07

TABLE 2. INFRARED AND MÖSSBAUER DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Infrared spectra			Mössbauer	
	Absorption band at cm^{-1} (H ₂ O)		(C $\equiv$ N)	Isomer shift mm/sec	quadruple splitting mm/sec
Compound of Fe(II) with $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6$	3340	1630	2135	+0.11	0.55
$\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_6$	3350	1630	2135	+0.23	0.65
$\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	3400	1640	2060	+0.09	0.51
Compound of Fe(III) with $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6$	3340	1620	2135	+0.11	0.55
$\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_6$	3350	1620	2135	+0.25	0.60
$\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	3450	1590	2060	+0.10	0.53

The important infrared spectral characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 2. All the complexes show a broad band around 3300 cm^{-1} and a medium intensity band at 1620 cm^{-1} both of which are due to water of crystallisation¹² (all these complexes contain two molecules of water of crystallisation). The $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency in $\text{K}_4\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_8$ and $\text{K}_4\text{W}(\text{CN})_8$ appears at 2120 cm^{-1} while on complexation with either $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$, this band appears at 2135 cm^{-1} . This behaviour is similar to that of iron blues where a single $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ frequency¹³ is observed at 2075 cm^{-1} irrespective of the fact that the iron blue is obtained from $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$. It may thus be concluded that iron is only in one valency state in these complexes and most probably in the +3 state. In the case of $\text{K}_3\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ band appears at 2080 cm^{-1} while its complexes with $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ again exhibit only one $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ frequency at 2060 cm^{-1} which again suggests only one valency state for iron in the two complexes.

The Mössbauer spectra of the complexes show that iron is in the +3 oxidation state (spin free) as they show characteristic values¹⁴ of isomer shift and quadruple splitting (Table 2), for spin free $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$. This confirms the view point that iron is in +3 oxidation state in the complexes irrespective of the fact that the complex is prepared from either $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$. The color change from yellow to blue in the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ complexes is thus also due to oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ to $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$. Since all these complexes are blue and iron is in the +3 oxidation state

(outside the coordination sphere) they are analogous to the iron blues (Prussian and Turnbull's blue) and hence they may be termed as 'Iron Blue Analogs'.

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